

Guidelines: Co-creation approaches for community, artists and scientists Deliverable 2.1.

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TIDAL
Arts

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
Art and Sciences

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Abstract	A practical guide to co-creation approaches that bring together artists, scientists, and citizens, combining best practices, field-based insights, and key challenges with concrete recommendations to support effective, transdisciplinary engagement.
Keywords	TIDAL ArtS; Co-creation; Participatory methods; Citizen engagement; Art-science collaboration; Social inclusivity; Pre-engagement; Transdisciplinarity; Best practices; Field-based learnings; Mission Ocean and Waters

Summary

This Co-Creation Guide has been developed within the framework of the TIDAL ArtS project to support collaborative processes between artists, scientists, and communities across Europe's [Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouse](#) areas. We believe that transformative environmental action requires new ways of working together, thus the guide provides a practical foundation for designing and implementing participatory artistic processes that are both socially inclusive and locally relevant. It emphasizes the importance of early and sustained engagement, supports the integration of diverse knowledge systems (including lived experience and scientific insight), and offers methods for involving communities not only in the making of artworks, but in shaping the process itself. The document is designed to be usable before, during, and after participatory activities, including workshops, artists' residencies, and community-based interventions. It includes guidance on identifying relevant actors, building trust, and working across differences, whether it be cultural, disciplinary, or geographical. Drawing from best practices in participatory arts, citizen science, and environmental engagement, the guide also reflects TIDAL ArtS' core ambition: to support new forms of collaboration that help communities reconnect with their aquatic environments in meaningful and creative ways. Likewise, the project contributes to the wider goals of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030," including increasing ocean literacy, supporting local stewardship, and mobilising culture as a source of knowledge and driver of change.

How to Use This Guide

This guide is designed to be practical and flexible. You can read it from start to finish to understand the full co-creation journey, or dip into specific sections as needed. The structure follows the stages of a co-creation process in arts-science collaborations: from preparation and community mapping, to design, facilitation, and follow-up. Look out for tip boxes, case examples, and checklists throughout.

Use it as a planning tool, a source of inspiration, or a reference when facing challenges. In detail, this guide begins with an introduction to Mission Ocean and Waters and its focus on participation, followed by a short review of methods and voices that shaped the guide.

From there, you'll find a series of field-based stories (Section 3), a synthesis of what we learned (Section 4), and a step-by-step approach to designing co-creation processes (Section 5). The Annexes at the end include a list of recommended methods, a quick guide for artists and our decalogue on co-creation. You can use the clickable table of contents to jump directly to any section.

This guide is intended to support the co-creation processes that will be implemented in TIDAL ArtS Work Package 4. It serves as a practical foundation for the participatory activities to be carried out in the Lighthouse Projects and TIDAL ArtS Residencies, ensuring that citizen engagement and co-creation remain central throughout the project.

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- [Macarena Marambio](#), Veterinarian, ICM-CSIC / Art4Sea
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- [Nora Mayr](#), Curator, CircEular / Klima Biennale Vienna
- [Vanessa Balagué](#), Marine Molecular Biologist, ICM-CSIC / Thalastasi
- [Vanessa Sarah Salvo](#), EMBIMOS Participatory information systems researcher and Posidonia Green Project scientific director, ICM-CSIC / Posidonia Green Festival

This guide was shaped by the stories and time they shared with us. We hope it reflects the same generosity, curiosity, and care they brought to the conversations.

1. Introduction

1.1. EU Mission Ocean & Waters, Lighthouses, and its focus on participation and social inclusion.

The European Union’s Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (“the Mission” or “Mission Ocean & Waters”) is an attempt to unite policy, industry, society and research behind the challenge of greatly improving the health of our aquatic ecosystems by the end of this decade. To do this, the Mission emphasizes the participation of society at large, through deliberation, citizen science activities, ocean literacy initiatives, and environmental management. In line with the Mission’s citizen engagement goals, this guide proposes a framework where scientists, artists, and citizens engage equally in shaping both the process and outcomes of local initiatives. By merging participatory science methods with participatory arts practices, it aims to foster inclusive, region-specific collaborations that are sensitive to local contexts while contributing to wider ocean restoration objectives. This guide was developed for the TIDAL ArtS project to support co-creation between artists, scientists, and communities within the EU Mission Ocean & Waters. It draws on interviews with practitioners, analysis of existing co-creation literature and toolkits to offer practical approaches tailored to the Mission’s goals¹.

1.2. What is TIDAL ArtS?

TIDAL ArtS is a project offering grants to artists, collectives, and creatives to support Mission Ocean and Waters. The Mission focuses on protecting and restoring the health of our ocean and waters. TIDAL ArtS seeks those who can combine art, science, and citizen engagement to connect communities with their ocean and waters through innovative artistic expressions and co-creation activities — thereby inspiring change and raising awareness about the challenges facing our waters.

At its core, TIDAL ArtS builds bridges between disciplines, cultures, and communities, by supporting innovative artistic practices that respond to the urgent challenges facing aquatic ecosystems. The project empowers artists to work alongside scientists, citizens, and local stakeholders, ensuring that diverse voices help shape the stories and solutions for our shared water futures.

As part of its mission, TIDAL ArtS has launched an open call to support 20 Lighthouse² Projects across Europe, each receiving a grant to develop participatory artworks rooted in local contexts. These projects are designed to be community-focused, socially inclusive, and engrained in environmental awareness.

¹ The EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” sets specific targets for citizen engagement, including empowering communities, promoting ocean literacy, supporting citizen science, and ensuring social inclusion and diversity. See: Mission Implementation Plan, p. 36. Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en

In addition, four Artistic Residencies - one in each of the Mission's Lighthouses² - will offer immersive opportunities for artists to collaborate closely with scientific institutions and community groups. These residencies provide space for deep interdisciplinary exchange and co-creation, allowing ideas to emerge through shared knowledge, lived experience, and artistic exploration.

TIDAL ArtS invites artists to become catalysts for change, working not just for communities, but with them, to imagine and shape resilient, water-conscious futures.

Mission Ocean & Water's main goal is to restore the health of our ocean and waters by 2030. To achieve this, it focuses on three key objectives:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
- Prevent and eliminate pollution
- Make the blue economy carbon-neutral and circular

The question we are dealing with in this guide is how to bring together scientific knowledge and artistic creativity in ways that genuinely include citizens, making them active partners instead of passive observers. The goal is to create strong, local "Lighthouse² communities" that feel ownership of the Mission's objectives and continue working toward a healthy ocean and water system even after 2030.

1.3. How this guide was made.

This guide was built from a mix of methods:

- Project mapping across Mission Ocean & Waters—related initiatives, a literature review on co-creation, art-science collaboration, and citizen participation.
- Interviews with artists, researchers including scientists from the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC), curators, mediators (professionals who facilitate dialogue and collaboration across disciplines or between communities and institutions).

While the project mapping helped us understand existing methods and tools, the core of this guide comes from the interviews. First, we share each project story on its own terms, and then we draw out the shared patterns, challenges, and lessons that emerged across them. Together, they offer both structure and lived experience to support co-creation in TIDAL ArtS.

2 The Mission Ocean & Waters defines four regional "Lighthouses" (Atlantic-Arctic, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic-North Sea, and Danube River-Black Sea basin) to pilot innovative actions and engage local communities in restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems. These Lighthouses serve as demonstration hubs for place-based solutions. (Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Plan, European Commission, 2021, pp. 7–8, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d6162cbd-6d09-48fd-b5b4-d7d2be69972c_en)

2. Co-creation practices in Mission Ocean & Waters

To develop this guide, we began by reviewing the methods and approaches developed by other projects under Mission Ocean & Waters to integrate co-creation and citizens into Mission activities. We focused on initiatives that bring together scientists, citizens, policymakers, and artists, and that are either already connected to the Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouses or offer practices that can be adapted to build inclusive and locally rooted collaborations. This section describes the diverse participatory approaches used in these projects to engage the actors through various methods aimed at addressing ocean and water challenges. It includes FLOW, PREP4BLUE, BlueMission AA, BlueMission BANOS, BlueMission Med, and Ocean Citizen.

Project: **Future Lives with Oceans and Waters (FLOW)**

Methods: **experiential futures workshops, semi-structured interviews, participatory mapping, role-playing games, and artistic co-creation.**

<https://www.flowhorizon.eu/re-surface-reimagine/>

The FLOW project explored how young people across Europe emotionally, culturally, and imaginatively relate to water in times of ecological crisis. FLOW created spaces for experiential futures thinking, inviting youth to co-create scenarios, stories, and sensory experiences that envision alternative water futures. The project positioned young people as active agents of transformation through participatory research, artistic expression, and foresight methodologies. FLOW came up with new ideas that can guide more inclusive, relational, and hope-filled engagements with aquatic ecosystems through playful yet profound encounters such as wearing blacked-out goggles to simulate oceanic blindness or drafting legal rights for rivers.

Project: **Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters (PREP4BLUE)**

Methods: **Surveys, citizen assemblies, scenario workshops, semi-structured interviews, walking interviews, and participatory mapping.**

<https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>

PREP4BLUE's goal is to show how citizens, scientists, and other groups can work together to protect and restore our ocean and waters. As part of this, PREP4BLUE created a toolbox that gives practical methods to involve citizens in Mission Ocean & Waters projects. The toolbox explains step-by-step how to prepare citizen engagement activities, how to run them, and how to monitor if they worked well. Methods include surveys, citizen assemblies, workshops, interviews, and participatory mapping. It is based on the idea that, for big challenges, where science alone is not enough, citizen participation is key. The toolbox is designed to be flexible, so that different regions and projects can adapt it to their needs.

Project: **Restoring our Ocean and Waters in the Atlantic & Arctic (BlueMissionAA)**

Method: **Citizen Assemblies, workshops and survey.**

https://bluemotionaa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/5.6Attachment_O.pdf

BlueMissionAA brings together a variety of participatory formats including scenario planning, storytelling workshops, collaborative mapping, and deliberative processes like citizen juries and consensus conferences. These are used as adaptable tools depending on the context. What stands out is the project's emphasis on mixing structured participation (like citizen assemblies) with more creative and locally rooted approaches. It's framed as a continuous dialogue between citizens, scientists, and institutions.

Project: **Supporting the EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters in the Baltic and North Sea (BlueMission BANOS)**

Method: **Collaborative platform: expert-led discussions, collaborative workshops, scenario planning.**

<https://bluemotionbanos.eu/>

This project organizes Mission Arenas, a collaborative platform where stakeholders, such as scientists, policymakers, businesses, and NGOs, gather to co-design solutions for sustainable water and ocean management. These arenas include expert-led discussions, collaborative workshops, and scenario planning to align interests and priorities. While the method is primarily stakeholder-driven, it has passive citizen participation, meaning community voices are represented through policymakers or advocacy groups rather than direct involvement. The approach is useful for structuring decision-making but requires additional adaptation to integrate artistic methodologies.

Project: **Supporting the Mediterranean Sea basin for the implementation of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters (BlueMissionMed)**

Method: **Co-Creation with Stakeholders.**

<https://bluemotionmed.eu/>

BlueMissionMed applies co-creation approaches, where scientists, policymakers, businesses, and citizens collaborate on pollution prevention strategies for the Mediterranean. The process begins with participatory workshops where local communities help identify key challenges, followed by brainstorming and prototyping solutions with expert guidance.

These methodologies ensure that final strategies combine scientific knowledge with local insights, making them practical and context-specific. Its participatory approach could be expanded to include creative methodologies within the art and science spectrum.

Project: **Ocean Citizen**

Method: **Transdisciplinary Approach to marine restoration.**

<https://oceancitizen.eu/results/deliverables/>

Ocean Citizen employs a transdisciplinary co-creation model that merges scientific research, artistic engagement, and local community participation to restore marine ecosystems. The project starts with community-driven participatory science, where local stakeholders contribute knowledge and engage in hands-on restoration efforts (i.e. seagrass replanting and biodiversity monitoring). Meanwhile, the project uses art-based methodologies, including public exhibitions, murals, performance storytelling, and interdisciplinary workshops, to make conservation accessible and emotionally resonant for a broader audience.

Closing reflections

Projects like FLOW and Ocean Citizen showed that local anchoring, emotional connection, and playful formats (like sensory walks or storytelling) can open participation in surprising ways. PREP4BLUE's toolbox gives step-by-step formats for citizen engagement, while BlueMission AA shows how assemblies can make policy personal. However, in most of the projects reviewed here, art came in at the end, to communicate results. TIDAL ArtS aims to go further, inviting artists to shape the questions, the spaces, and the relationships from the start. Scenario planning, public storytelling, youth co-design, role-play or artistic residencies, when combined with shared intention and sensitive facilitation, can create spaces where real collaboration unfolds.

This review connects our guide to the broader Mission Ocean & Waters landscape, offering inspiration and direction as TIDAL ArtS has launched its calls.

While these projects offer useful models and structured approaches that align specifically with the Mission, the following section turns to insights gathered directly from practitioners, artists, scientists, and mediators, who have worked directly in projects, often at smaller and more experimental scales.

3. Who we spoke to

To anchor this guide in real experience, we gathered a series of interviews with practitioners who have lived through the highs, lows, and beautiful messiness of art-science-citizen collaboration. Each project featured here brings its approach between residencies, festivals, education programs, activist networks, or experimental labs. Together, they offer a window into how it's designed, how people are engaged, what makes it work (or not), and what we can learn for the future.

Below is a list of the artists, scientists, mediators, and curators we spoke with, each of whom shared their time, experience, and reflections to help shape this guide.

Name	Profile	Affiliation / Project	Summary
1 Vanessa Balagué	Marine Molecular Biologist	ICM-CSIC / Thalastasi	Project coordinator who oversaw the logistics and facilitation of the art-science collaboration, ensuring the smooth development of Thalastasi to transform genomic and environmental data into immersive sound and visuals.
2 Elisabetta Broglio	Curator, Researcher	ICM-CSIC / Art and Science Projects	Curated performative science-art experiences, that used performance to make ocean research experiential.
3 Jordi Brunet	Eufònic's Executive Producer	Eufònic Festival / Co-Vision	Developed participatory methods to engage festivalgoers and local communities in mapping emotional geographies of the Delta del Ebre.
4 Eduardo Castillo-Vinuesa	Director of TBA21-Academy	TBA21-Academy / Organismo	Directed a transdisciplinary platform focusing on care, ecological thinking, and experimental forms of collective authorship.

Name	Profile	Affiliation / Project	Summary
5 Aleksandra Czerniak	Art Historian, Digital transformation manager	TBA21 / OCEAN / UNI. Activations Webs of Water in collaboration with Laura Ranca (Tactical Tech's Exposing the Invisible), Federico Pérez Villoro	Helped evolve a research fellowship into a more collaborative, emotionally attuned co-creation process
6 Isidora Fernandez	Science & Art specialist, PULSE Art project coordinator	Science for Change / Forensic River sanctuary media	Designed flexible, youth-led co-creation projects in socially vulnerable neighborhoods using citizen science and participatory tools.
7 Nicole Loeser	Director, Institute for Art and Innovation	Institute for Art and Innovation / Sustainable Coastal Futures	Bridged policy, evaluation, and creative practice through structured pilot actions and systemic collaboration.
8 Macarena Marambio	Veterinarian	ICM-CSIC / Art4Sea	Coordinated short-term artistic residencies on Mediterranean islands connecting local communities, marine science, and creative expression.
9 Nora Mayr	Curator	CircEUlar / Klima Biennale Vienna	Curated science-art collaborations as part of a biennial focused on circular economies and climate futures.
10 Marta Royo	Scientist, Artist, Mediator	ICM-CSIC, Shook studio / Thalastasi	Helped translate complex microbial and oceanographic data into more accessible language, supporting the creation of Thalastasi, a generative audiovisual installation that showcases the invisible role of marine microbes in climate regulation.

Name	Profile	Affiliation / Project	Summary
T1 Vanessa Sarah Salvo	EMBIMOS Participatory information systems researcher and Posidonia Green Project Scientific Director	ICM-CSIC / Posidonia Green Festival	Hosted art-based initiatives during the Posidonia Green Festival called "Som Blau", a participatory workshop that uses sound and metaphor to help students decode climate change narratives and rethink how we communicate science.

Each of these voices appears throughout the following pages, not always quoted directly, but always present in the insights shared.

3.1. Interviews methodology

A first set of interviews engaged scientists from the Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC) who had coordinated and participated in art-science-citizen projects to gain first-hand insights on their challenges and suggestions for successful interdisciplinary collaborations. As a second step, interviews were conducted with a broader community including artists, curators and mediators discussing their related projects which allowed to expand the insights beyond the scientific community. Interviews were conducted in Spanish or English, based on each participant's language preference, to ensure a more natural and comfortable exchange. The interviews were recorded with prior consent from all participants and transcribed using Otter.ai and Google Doc transcription, to ensure accuracy and fidelity to the speakers' words. The data was analysed using thematic framework analysis; initial coding was performed manually to identify recurring concepts, unique expressions, and challenges. Themes were refined iteratively by clustering them into broader categories such as best practices, lessons learned and challenges with recommendations. To support the organisation and synthesis of insights, ChatGPT was used to test thematic clusters and explore alternative framings. Its utilisation was restricted to this purpose, and it did not replace human analysis, and all interpretations remained rooted in the original transcripts. This use follows EU guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research.

Why the interviews?

The interviews helped us understand how co-creation plays out in the field. We wanted to hear the behind-the-scenes:

- What worked?
- What didn't?
- What advice would you give someone starting now?

Our objectives were:

- To explore how participation unfolds across different formats and contexts,
- To uncover the challenges and unexpected moments that arise during co-creative processes,
- To gather field-based insights that don't always make it into formal reports,
- To understand when and how different people (artists, scientists, citizens) were involved,
- To translate co-creation from a theoretical methodology into something lived, felt, and practiced in real contexts.

Insights from these interviews are synthesised in Section 4, where we explore key challenges and practical strategies from real co-creation experiences. The quotes and patterns gathered in the rest of the sections are intended to support anyone who wants to build truly participatory projects in the context of Mission Ocean, or beyond.

We spoke with eleven practitioners practicing on the ground art, science, and community engagement. Through semi-structured interviews, we explored how they design participatory processes and create connections between disciplines. These conversations took us from a neighborhood in North Troy (New York, USA) where youth co-designed environmental interventions, to the Ebro Delta (Spain) where artists and scientists mapped the emotional cartography of wetlands, to Ustica Island (Italy) where local fishermen, curators, and dancers shared rituals to honour the sea. Each person we spoke with had experience in running or curating participatory processes: artistic residencies, citizen science actions, interspecies walks, embodied workshops, open calls, and experimental fellowships. What united all the practitioners was a commitment to actively create participation.

“We talk about participation, but our systems are not designed for it.”
— Practitioner interviewed.

Since the aim was mainly to gather insights, interviews followed a semi-structured approach. We asked about challenges, messy moments, unexpected breakthroughs, and how participation unfolded in real life. Exploratory questions included:

- What were the roles of each stakeholder?
- How did participation evolve throughout the project?
- Was there a key moment when collaboration transformed?
- Any unexpected outcomes?
- Was there a lasting impact or continued collaboration?
- Who was missing, and why?
- What's something you'd never do again in a co-creation project?

3.2 What practitioners told us

In the current section, you'll find a series of stories from the interviews showing how co-creation actually happens on the ground. From festivals to residencies, workshops to youth labs, these field insights show what worked, what was messy, and what helped people move forward. Each project eventually reflects a different way of building collaboration across art, science, and community.

Project No. 1

Project Type: Artist-scientist collaboration / Data-driven generative art

Project title: **Thalastasi**

Link: <https://www.icm.csic.es/en/news/art-and-science-merge-thalastasi-new-installation-gives-visibility-marine-microorganisms>

Interviewees: Vanessa Balagué and Marta Royo, Scientist and ArtSci

Location: Barcelona, Spain

What is the project about:

Thalastasi was an experiment in transforming marine data into generative sound and visuals. It focused on deep collaboration between artists and scientists, supported by mediation and technical adaptation, however it lacked the public engagement component.

Methodology

The Thalastasi project employed a co-creative methodology where scientists and artists collaborated to translate marine microbiology data into immersive artistic experiences. This collaboration emerged organically because both scientists and artists were using the same software tools for data analysis and creative visualization, creating an easy starting point for dialogue and exchange. The process is structured utilizing data-driven visual and sound design to highlight the role of marine microbes in climate regulation. The methodology integrates scientific mediation, artistic transformation, technological innovation, and project dissemination with a structured workflow that includes:

- Data from an oceanographic expedition was filtered using different software programs.
- Both scientists and artists used tools like Processing and Blender to transform raw genetic and physicochemical data into generative art.
- Scientific mediators helped bridge the knowledge gap, ensuring that artists could engage with the data while maintaining scientific integrity.
- The project narrative followed a vertical journey through the ocean, using data to build a sound and visual composition that metaphorically represents microbial processes involved in climate regulation.
- The final output was an immersive installation, using audiovisual elements to communicate complex environmental processes to a broader audience.

The artistic team explored different data transformation techniques through an iterative process of trial and error.

Key players

- Scientists: Provided data, training, and feedback to artists.
- Artists: Translated scientific data into creative outputs.
- Mediators: Facilitated discussions and transformed data.
- Project Coordinators: Logistics, structured the process.
- Festival Organizers: Helped showcase final artistic expressions.

What worked well

- The project was disseminated in different contexts including scientific conferences, art and design universities, and cultural festivals, serving as a model of art-science collaboration to explore and develop new channels and formats for scientific communication.
- Scientists and mediators prepared educational resources to help artists understand complex datasets.
- Graphs and plots were provided to enhance comprehension of ocean dynamics.
- The project evolved through trial and error, allowing artists to engage with data at their own pace.
- Transparent communication on time commitment and workload was essential.
- The project was showcased in rural areas where cultural and scientific activities are less common, aiming to broaden access to such experiences.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Artists had a hard time interpreting scientific data.
→ Scientists with the mediator created visualized datasets and provided training materials.
- Lack of formal evaluation of impact.
→ Impact was measured informally through social media engagement and media coverage.
- Artists had to be "chased" for deadlines, leading to uneven workloads.
→ Early transparency on availability and work styles helped set realistic expectations.

"It would have been great if someone from outside had observed the process."
— Vanessa Balagué

Smart tags

- Method & Format: Data transformation, Generative sound/visual
- Who Was Involved: Scientists, Artists, Mediators
- Thematic Focus: Microbiology, Ocean data
- Process Style: Iterative, Tech-enabled
- Participation: None (artist-scientist only)

Project(s) No. 2

Project Type: Short-form labs / Hybrid performance-based art-science

Project titles: **A, B and C**

Link: [N/A](#)

Interviewee: Elisabetta Broglio³, Curator, Researcher, ICM-CSIC

Location: Barcelona, Spain

2.1. Project A:

Project A is an artistic residency combining science and performing arts to engage the public in an experiential and emotional understanding of scientific research. Some scientific lecturers were invited at the beginning to introduce key themes. Artists developed performances based on scientific input. A physical challenge was incorporated to increase artist's engagement and the collected data was later used by one of the scientists involved in the project. A mediator participated throughout to guide integration. At the end of their two-week residency, a performance was made by the artists where the public has an active role to play. It was followed by a round table with mixed artists, scientists and the public.

"Above all, we learned how important it is to share knowledge from a neutral space to connect more closely." — Elisabetta Broglio

2.2. Project B

A two-day art-science laboratory where 20 artists from various disciplines collaborate with scientists to explore the functions of marine ecosystems. Participants developed new artistic languages to represent marine interdependence through biomimicry-based movement workshops and interactive discussions. The project concluded in a public performance and expert roundtable, emphasizing how art can make invisible ecological processes tangible and inspire environmental awareness.

2.3. Project C

As a continuation of the first laboratory, there was an interest in further exploring the theme with some of the artists who participated in the previous project. This new project aimed to translate complex biological processes into visceral, sensory experiences through video art, dance, and performative interventions.

³ Elisabetta Broglio was interviewed for three projects with similar characteristics at the same time.

Key Players:

- Emerging and established artists
- Scientists from various research groups
- Curators
- Project organizers and coordinators
- Artistic performative team
- A scientifically informed assistant director

What worked well

- Design an immersive activity that allows for exchange beyond formal talks.
- The presence of a scientific coordinator who supports the scientific team in their relationship with the artists.
- Curators' active engagement during initial workshops helped artists feel supported and grounded in the scientific themes.
- This role was particularly effective in navigating challenges organizing emotional debriefing and reflection sessions after tensions arose, which helped restore cohesion.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped (or would have helped)

- Scientists often just leave after their talks not having a clear idea of what else they can contribute.
 - Assigning scientists specific, continuous roles throughout the project would have made them feel more comfortable.
- Some couldn't see the value in scientists "sticking around during the process".
 - Foster a shared introduction phase where organizers, artists, and scientists exchange expectations, building mutual understanding from the start.
- Public participation was punctual and limited (only during the event).
 - Integrate public engagement as an ongoing element, open rehearsals, interactive workshops, or feedback sessions with citizens before the final performance.
- Lack of planning and anticipation for the collaboration process.
 - Co-create a detailed roadmap early on, including stages for artist-scientist exchanges, creative development, public interaction, and evaluation.
- No legacy or continuation after the project ended.
 - Think of formats that allow space for publishing learnings, and archive artistic-scientific outcomes.

Project No. 3

Project Type: Festival platform, Local environmental engagement

Project title: **Co-Vision**

Link: <https://eufonic.net/es/covision/>

Interviewee: Jordi Brunet, Eufònic's Executive Producer

Location: Ebro Delta, Spain

What is the project about:

Co-Vision is a European cooperation project that aims to co-create and co-produce cultural content and a digital artistic archive focused on environmental challenges, engaging citizens, artists, and local entities through a participatory cultural strategy. Within Co-Vision, the Eufònic festival focuses on the Ebro Delta, using debates, scientific insights, and art to explore how climate change is transforming the territory and to involve locals in shaping new narratives.

Methodology

Co-Vision brings together scientists, artists, and local communities to imagine the future of their territories under climate change. Each festival chooses a pressing local issue (like land loss in the Ebro Delta), partners with a scientific institution for guidance, and hosts live debates with stakeholders, (from fishermen to ecologists). Artists listen in, take notes, and transform these conversations into creative works, while the process is documented through drawings, recordings, and reflections to build a shared, evolving narrative. The methodology integrates local debates, scientific input, and artistic co-creation. Each festival partners with a scientific institution (e.g., Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA) for the Ebro Delta) to guide discussions with factual research.

"It was important to anchor the debate in something concrete—how climate change will affect festivals and the territory that hosts them."

— Jordi Brunet

Key Players

- Scientific institutions (e.g. Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology - IRTA)
- Curator
- Local associations (e.g. fishers' cooperatives)
- Community members and residents
- Educational institutions

What worked well

- Each festival partners with a scientific expert or institution to provide credibility and depth to discussions.
- Collaboration with cooperatives, associations, and local policymakers strengthens community trust.
- Direct invitations and personal outreach from local networks.
- Introduce activities in schools to involve young participants.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Holding debates in scientific institutions (e.g., IRTA) discouraged participation.
→ Moving them to public, accessible spaces is necessary.
- Timing of events (work hours, summer holidays).
→ Schedule debates in the evening or on weekends to fit citizen availability.
- Festivalgoers may not transition to debates
→ Integrate debates as part of festival programming rather than separate events.
- Institutional mistrust (e.g., regional government absence).
→ Increase visibility and engage local policymakers more effectively.
- Policymakers are difficult to engage because they fear being criticized or blamed as part of the problem.
→ Create safe, constructive spaces that encourage their participation by focusing on shared solutions.

Smart Tags:

- Method & Format: Community mapping, public debates
- Who Was Involved: Artists, scientists, local residents
- Thematic Focus: Climate change, Delta ecosystems
- Process Style: Regionally tailored, Festival-based
- Participation: Active and passive

Project No. 4

Project Type: Research and Infrastructural activism

Project title: **Organismo**

Link: <https://tba21.org/organismoyearone>

Interviewee: Eduardo Castillo-Vinuesa, Director of TBA21-Academy

Location: Europe

What is the project about:

Organismo is a two-year experiment where artists, scientists, and architects dive into real-world challenges ranging from forest governance to ocean rights through collaborative research. Over 10 case studies have been completed, addressing topics like self-governance of forests, museum evolution, and ocean conservation.

Methodology

Organismo is a two-year experimental platform initiated by TBA21 that brings together artists, scientists, communities, and institutions to collaboratively explore environmental and social questions. It starts by forming diverse teams through open calls and interviews, selecting people based on how they behave and collaborate, not just on their CVs. These teams then meet regularly to work across disciplines using creative tools like storytelling, prototyping, and collective reflection. One major project that came out of Organismo is a science-fiction film imagining future ocean governance, activism, and cultural heritage. This film becomes a political tool and will be screened at the 2025 UN Ocean Conference, helping to open new ways of thinking about legal and environmental systems and trigger conversations. The current project continues this exploration through another film-based prototype, focusing on ocean-related legal questions, using narrative strategies, and building connections through residencies and collaborative workshops.

"We invite people to wear the jacket they want" — Eduardo Castillo-Vinuesa

Key Players

- Artists
- Scientists
- Cultural practitioners
- Legal experts
- Community members
- Representatives from institutions like museums or international organizations

What worked well

- Prioritize the design of the team before the design of the content, group chemistry and shared ethics come first.
- Using artistic outputs (films, workshops) as instruments for dialogue and legislative backcasting⁴.
- Use weekly collaborative sessions to create continuity, trust, and room for iteration.
- Focus on how people work together rather than just their technical expertise.
- Curate for how people work together, not just what they know.

"The best five individuals don't always make the best group."

— Eduardo Castillo-Vinuesa

Big (and small) realizations and what helped (or would have helped)

- Keeping people engaged over the long term.
→ Create a steady, meaningful rhythm that keeps people connected and makes them want to show up.
- Rushing to simplify complex issues.
→ Give the process space to hold complexity. Don't force it into neat boxes, take time to pause, reflect, and make sense of things together.

Smart Tags:

- Method & Format: Investigative workshops, Group prototyping, Open call
- Who Was Involved: Artists, Scientists, Activists, Data Scientists, Citizen Researchers
- Thematic Focus: Water literacy, Climate justice
- Process Style: Co-created, Question-led, Adaptive
- Participation: Active / Self-directed

⁴ Legislative backcasting: a method where you start from a future goal and work backwards, using existing laws and scientific knowledge to imagine how we could get there.

Project No. 5

Project Type: Collaborative Workshop activation series / Investigative cross-disciplinary Art-Science Format

Project title: **Activation series (OCEAN / UNI)**

Link: <https://tba21.org/websofwater>

Interviewee: Aleksandra Czerniak, Art Historian, Digital transformation manager at TBA21

Location: International/Nomadic

What is the project about:

After several years of running OCEAN / UNI - TBA21's learning initiative and open platform for dialogue between artists, scientists, activists and ocean practitioners, it became clear to Aleksandra and her team that the standard lecture series format needed to be complemented with something more interactive and hands-on. "We needed a space where we could actively apply what we had learned over the years at OCEAN / UNI and explore how to build relationships between art and science" she said.

Working with Tactical Tech's Exposing⁵ the Invisible and Federico Pérez Villoro, the team developed a format where artists, scientists, and activists collaborate in real time to examine the intersections of technological infrastructures, freshwater scarcity and water distribution issues in the Caribbean.

Methodology

- Open Call: Participants were selected for their experience in artistic research, scientific analysis, and data storytelling.
- Guiding Questions: Each session is structured around open questions following investigative journalism and activism: What are the abuses? What are the problems? What are the places? What are the actors? What are the economics? What are the relationships?
- Group Work and Prototyping: Interdisciplinary teams explored the same questions from different perspectives, developing tools, mappings, or narratives.
- Digital Residency: A parallel digital residency allowed participants to engage remotely, share resources, and co-develop ideas asynchronously, ensuring continuous collaboration.

Although the activation series is being produced remotely, the current program focuses on Caribbean contexts and actively includes participants from the region.

"It is very important that that both artistic and scientific voices are talking equally together." — Aleksandra Czerniak

⁵ A non-profit organisation that aims to empower young people to take control of their digital futures through education and co-creation. <https://tacticaltech.org/>

Key Players

- Artists, Scientists, Journalists, Biohackers, Data analysts, Environmental engineers, Sonic ethnographers, Architects, Activists, Chemists, Software developers, Cartographers, and curators: joined as participants and co-creators.
- Mentors: support group dynamics and ensure continuity.
- Tactical Tech's Exposing Invisible and other partners: brought investigative and tech-based methodologies.
- Citizens: engaged through open calls and local events; some become key contributors.

What worked well

- The open call broadened the network, attracting an unusually interdisciplinary community (see key players), all united by a shared interest in water.
- Framing around investigative questions gives participants a clear, shared direction to co-create from, ensuring focus while leaving space for multiple perspectives.
- By connecting art to action, activations aim not just to express ideas artistically but to influence policy or local communities.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Same goals, different languages.
When different disciplines come together, misunderstandings may happen, especially when no one is translating the jargon.
→ Use simpler language, shared context, and commit to clarity across disciplines.
- Strong dialogue, limited realization.
While OCEAN / UNI maintained its main lecture series, conversation alone was not enough.
→ The activations introduced new formats (shared questions, collaborative investigation) to move beyond lectures.
- Co-creation from the start.
Early formats sometimes felt like artists were just there to “translate” others’ work.
→ All participants, artists, scientists, and activists help define the problem, not just illustrate the solution.
- Create a light rhythm of check-ins to hold the process gently.
→ Offer consistent check-ins to maintained momentum and structure, while still leaving space for initiative and autonomy.
- Context matters. Designing from a distance led to disconnects. Do not design for a place without its people. Working on Caribbean issues from Europe did not feel right.
→ Bring in regional voices from the start.

Project No. 6

Project Type: Citizen science / Youth-led participatory mapping

Project title: **Forensic River: Community Science & Water Justice**

Link: <https://www.mediasanctuary.org/event/community-science-water-justice-with-isidora-fernandez/>

Interviewee: Isidora Fernandez, Sci&Art specialist, PULSE Art Project coordinator

Location: North Troy, NY, USA

What is the project about:

The Forensic River Project transformed a community science lab into a lively, crime scene investigation where residents played detectives to track down environmental threats in their rivers and coastal waters. It combined art, science, and local wisdom and encouraged people to become guardians of their aquatic environment, reconnecting them emotionally and personally to the water around them.

Methodology

The methodology centres on flexible, process-driven co-creation, where artists, scientists, and local communities collaboratively design participatory projects. It took place at Nature Lab in North Troy, NY, USA, a conflictive neighbourhood with high social vulnerability, where the project engaged local youth already involved in citizen science initiatives. The approach adapted to local needs and values, avoiding pre-defined frameworks. Through participatory mapping, participants use transparent overlays to mark underwater beauty, interactive storytelling through performances, and gamification of scientific data collection, such as transforming a lab into a forensic crime scene to engage participants.

Key Players

- Children and youth: Participated actively in citizen science activities and artistic co-creation
- Community leaders & NGOs: Helped facilitate engagement, provided institutional support
- Local media (radio, newspapers): Used to create intrigue and boost participation
- Artist and mediator: Led creative engagement, created methodologies to community needs

"Scientists and artists must co-create, not just use art to 'translate' science." — Isidora Fernandez

What worked well

- Spending time embedded in the space before introducing an external project.
- No rigid approach was imposed; instead, it adapts to local knowledge, materials, and participation styles.
- Merging citizen science with artistic practices helped make environmental issues more tangible. Creating interactive experiences (e.g., forensic crime scene, whale migration mapping) increased participation.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Community engagement was low at first.
→ Spent two months attending local sessions to build curiosity before launching the project.
- Middle-aged adults were underrepresented.
→ Engage parents of participating children, bring in community leaders.
- Some participants were sceptical of the project's relevance.
→ Frame engagement through a gamified forensic approach to spark curiosity.
- Ensuring sustainability after the artist leaves.
→ Structured projects so that locals could continue them independently.
Be open to contact thereafter.

"The final result is not always polished, and that's okay. It's about the experience, not the final product." — Isidora Fernandez

Key Players

- Method & Format: Participatory mapping, Gamification, Role play
- Who Was Involved: Youth, Educators, Scientists, Artist mediator
- Thematic Focus: Water justice, Urban pollution
- Process Style: Community-led, Adaptive
- Participation: Active

Project No. 7

Project Type: Scenario-based co-design / Policy foresight

Project title: **Sustainable Coastal Futures**

Link: <https://universal-sea.org/prep-4-blue>

Interviewee: Nicole Loeser, Director, Institute for Art and Innovation

Location: Berlin, Germany

What is the project about:

Sustainable Coastal Futures is a foresight-driven, transdisciplinary initiative, co-developed by the Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI) and EUCC - The Coastal Union Germany, invited citizens, scientists, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to imagine coastal futures together. IFAI facilitated participatory, art-based methods while EUCC-D contributed expertise on marine systems. Using empathy mapping, world-building, and visual storytelling, the project enabled participants to design imaginative yet actionable visions for 2050. The process emphasized emotional engagement and shared agency, democratizing conversations around policy and systemic change.

Methodology

The project employed the Art for Futures Lab, a participatory foresight method combining artistic practice with systems thinking. Techniques included Future-Prototyping (tangible interventions for possible futures), World-Building (shared speculative environments grounded in science and local narratives), Empathy Mapping (capturing diverse perspectives, often underrepresented), and Backcasting (working backwards from preferred futures to action steps). Workshops used mood boards, AI-generated images, and hand-drawn sketches to make complex ideas like decarbonization and energy transitions accessible and emotionally resonant. The approach centered on co-design, dialogue, and collective imagination, legitimizing emerging ideas in policy contexts.

Key Players

- Citizens and coastal communities
- Environmental and social scientists, researchers
- Industry representatives (e.g., energy sector, hydrogen production)
- Civil society organizations and NGOs
- Policymakers and regional authorities
- Artists and creative professionals

What worked well

- The co-creative process encouraged open dialogue and negotiation around offshore hydrogen production, helping participants navigate uncertainty, voice concerns, and explore common ground.
- Imaginative foresight methods supported a shift from problem-centric thinking to a shared vision of positive coastal futures. This not only increased engagement but also built acceptance for innovative solutions such as regenerative energy infrastructures.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Late confirmation of the venue limited outreach, especially to youth.
→ Confirm venues earlier and build in time for deeper community outreach, especially through schools, youth orgs, and local hangouts. Also, keep hybrid options open for those who can't attend in person.
- Debates over "green" hydrogen emerged due to differing levels of technical understanding.
→ Embrace disagreement as a learning moment. Facilitation and scientific input were key to keeping the dialogue constructive and focused on shared values. Hold space for diverse opinions, without letting the conversation get stuck.
- Terms like "decarbonization" or "energy systems" were intimidating for some participants, especially those with no technical background.
→ Use narrative and visual tools to anchor complex terms in lived experiences and local relevance and make these ideas easier to grasp and more fun to explore.
- Not enough representation from the broader region.
→ Plan ahead with a broader regional outreach strategy. This could mean partnering with grassroots orgs, offering travel support for participants coming from further away, or decentralization strategies.

Smart tags:

- Method & Format: Participatory Foresight, Empathy Mapping, World-Building
- Who Was Involved: Citizens, Scientists, Policymakers, Industry, Creatives
- Thematic Focus: Coastal resilience, Energy transition, Ocean literacy
- Process Style: Structured, Imaginative, Inclusive
- Participation: Active

Project No. 8

Project Artistic residency / Island-based environmental storytelling

Project title: **Art4Sea**

Link: <https://art4sea.eu/#the-project>

Interviewee: Macarena Marambio, Veterinarian, ICM-CSIC

Location: Alonissos, Gozo, and Ustica Islands

What is the project about:

Art4Sea brought artists to three Mediterranean islands to creatively explore ocean issues. Through short residencies, artists reimagined marine science using murals, underwater sculptures, and digital art, often shaped by their interactions with island communities.

Methodology

Artists were selected through an open call and invited to spend time in Mediterranean island environments, where they explored underwater worlds, connected with local traditions, and received mentoring. Online meetings were organized beforehand between artists, scientists, and partners to align expectations and share practical information. Scientists introduced key themes about ocean health and local marine ecosystems. The residency model combined one-week stays with field visits, diving/snorkelling activities, shared meals, cultural exchanges, and structured sessions like Ocean Health workshops and “Meet the Artists” events. Mentoring was offered across three axes: scientific (marine ecosystems and threats), technical (digital tools, underwater equipment), and artistic development. Citizens influenced the residencies indirectly through local stories, traditions, and feedback. After the on-site experience, artists entered a preparation phase at home to finalize their works, culminating in installations and public presentation in a final event. Focus groups and interviews captured reflections from citizens, scientists, and artists, highlighting expanded understandings of marine realities and cross-sector collaboration.

"We need to align the languages and also to align the goals." — Macarena Marambio

Key Players

Coordinating partners, scientific mentors, artistic mentors, local authorities, marine conservation bodies, cultural institutions, tourism operators, diving centres, and community representatives. The interviewee was the point of contact with the artists and the scientific community.

What worked well

- Artists engaged with local communities through cultural visits and meetings with local stakeholders.
- Online training sessions provided foundational knowledge on marine sciences and copyright issues.
- The project included digital, street-art, and underwater artworks to increase accessibility.
- Establishing WhatsApp groups for ongoing communication.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped

- Some communities actively participated, while others showed little interest.
→ Conduct pre-engagement activities to assess interest. Involve local leaders early to co-design activities and ensure relevance.
- Not all artists and not all residency sites interacted with local fishermen and cultural representatives.
→ A community liaison could ensure more meaningful participation, helping locals feel more included in the process.
- Language barriers made it difficult for artists to engage with local communities, especially in Alonissos (Greek-speaking) and Ustica (Italian-speaking).
→ Hire translators or local mediators to facilitate communication. Consider bilingual project coordinators.
- Some artists struggled to integrate local cultural elements. Many arrived with a pre-planned concept rather than adapting their work based on local engagement.
→ Extend the residency duration or add an exploration phase before artistic creation. Provide pre-project briefings on cultural adaptability.
- Short-term residencies limited deep cultural exchange. Seven days were not enough for digital artists to fully engage with local communities.
→ Consider a hybrid model: a short initial residency with follow-up virtual engagements, or multiple site visits over time.
- Weather-dependent art forms (murals, sculptures) faced delays. Rain threatened mural completion.
→ Build flexibility into the timeline or provide alternative locations (e.g., covered walls, indoor spaces). Allocate buffer time for weather disruptions.

- Low participation in post-training evaluations.
 - Make feedback completion mandatory for certification. Conduct evaluations in person during the residency rather than afterward.
- Ownership of artistic works needs clear legal agreements. Uncertainty over who controls murals and sculptures led to legal concerns.
 - Develop clear contracts defining ownership, usage rights, and conditions for modification, relocation, or removal.
- Scientists had restricted availability, making it difficult to provide personalized guidance to every artist. They could not always provide in-depth answers to all artists' inquiries, as some topics fell outside their areas of specialization.
 - Provide a library of short videos, articles, and pre-answered FAQs categorized by theme (e.g., marine species, pollution, ocean policy). Create a networked pool of experts.
- While the training was mandatory, it was difficult to verify whether all artists actively engaged with the content.
 - Gamify participation: Offer badges or certificates for completing different content modules, which can be shared on social media or added to CVs. Ask artists to briefly present how the training influenced their project idea, through a shared forum or short video pitch.

Smart tags:

- Method & Format: Artistic residency, Community interviews
- Who Was Involved: Artists, Scientists, Local authorities
- Thematic Focus: Seagrass, Ocean culture
- Process Style: Short-term, Immersive
- Participation: Active

Project No. 9

Project Type: Curated art-science pairings / Data translation and reflection

Project title: **CircEULAR: "Sensing Resonance"**

Link: <https://circeular.org/klima-biennale-wien-2024-x-circeular-sensing-resonance/>

Interviewee: Nora Mayr, Curator

Location: Austria, Klima Biennale Wien

What is the project about:

Nora Mayr curated art-science pairings that were about translating complex data into shared experiences. She helped scientists and artists slow down, connect, and rethink how knowledge moves through curated reflection. The results of the artistic reflections and dialogues were presented during the Vienna Climate Summit at Klima Biennale Wien 2024.

Methodology

The "Sensing Resonance" project aimed to foster collaboration between artists and researchers from the CircEULAR project, which investigates circular economy strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Nora acted as a mediator and curator and selected four scientific research projects out of 15 options based on their accessibility and creative potential. Artists were chosen by the mediator rather than conducting an open call. She was looking for possible connection points within the research projects for artists: the overall research topic, a specific research question, or the method that had been used, as well as the research material that had the potential to spark artistic interest. The research projects focused on circular economy research, including datasets on European building stocks and sociological studies on why people engage in circular practices. The process consisted of initial meetings where scientists explained their research, and artists were given freedom to respond creatively without direct scientific oversight.

"The scientists and artists who built personal connections were more engaged in the project." — Nora Mayr

Key Players

- Scientists: Provided datasets and explanations of circular economy research.
- Artists: Responded creatively to the data with full artistic freedom.
- Mediator: Curated the projects, selected artists, and facilitated communication.
- CircEULAR Klima Biennale Wien 2024: Provided funding, infrastructure, and support for exhibitions.
- Audience: Participating at the Vienna Climate Summit; scientists, educators and the general public.

What worked well

- Choosing scientific projects with strong artistic potential ensures better engagement (curation).
- Choose a theme or a project that has at least one connection point with the artist's practice and interest (medium, data, research question, topic).
- Artists were given full freedom to interpret scientific data.
- Finding artists familiar with scientific methodologies (e.g., working with data algorithms) improved collaboration.
- Scientists who personally connected with artists were more engaged.
- The project influenced research direction; an artist asked for the addition of Eastern European interviews, which is a profile that was missing.

Big (and small) realizations and what would help

- Not enough feedback loops between scientists and artists at the end.
→ Hold reflection sessions halfway through and at the end of the project.
- Scientists were surprised by final artworks.
→ Bridge expectations with more structured interim meetings could have helped.
- No formal impact assessment.
→ Proposed post-project interviews and documentation for future projects.
- No clear agreement on artwork reuse.
→ Legal contracts should predefine exhibition rights for a set period.

"I invited everyone to my place for dinner. The scientists and artists, who lived close to Vienna, came. It was very nice because, in the end, it's about building trust between people entering unfamiliar worlds, science or art. You need trust to really share." — Nora Mayr

Smart tags

- Method & Format: Art-science pairing, Data interpretation
- Who Was Involved: Scientists, Artists, Curators
- Thematic Focus: Circular economy
- Process Style: Curated, Reflective
- Participation: Passive

Project No. 10

Project Type: Climate communication / Art and education for sustainability

Project title: **Posidonia Green Festival, Project “Som Blau”**

Link: <https://posidoniagreenfestival.com/index.php/programa-barcelona-2024/>

Interviewee: Vanessa Sarah Salvo, EMBIMOS Participatory information systems researcher, Posidonia Green Project Scientific Director

Location: Barcelona, Spain

What is the project about:

The Posidonia Green Project is an international organisation that coordinates several projects, including the Posidonia Green Festival. Posidonia Festival is a cultural event for sustainability that uses music, metaphors, and creative workshops to foster dialogue. Within this festival, the Som Blau project engaged students and citizens by turning environmental data into rhythm and story, helping them connect emotionally with the climate crisis.

“It’s about creating poetic moments that make you reflect, without telling you what to think. We keep failing in climate communication because we speak only with rational facts.” — Vanessa Sarah Salvo

Methodology

The Posidonia Green Festival, held in Italy and Spain, celebrates art, environment, and community, focusing on environmental awareness and ocean literacy through art, science, and dialogue. From this spirit came “Som Blau” (We Are Blue), a Barcelona workshop coordinated by Eco-union, Posidonia Green Project, and ICM-CSIC, with Surfrider España, bringing together journalists, scientists, public institutions, and creatives to rethink climate narratives. Participants explored what climate change “sounds like,” using music and metaphor to connect science with emotion, with scientists and communicators co-creating ways to make climate and ocean issues resonate.

Key Players

- Media professionals
- Public institutions
- Environmental organizations
- Creatives
- Scientists and science communicators

What worked well

- The workshop brought together scientists, journalists, creatives, and institutions that are people who don't usually get to think together.
- When communicators had to think like scientists, and vice versa, it broke habits and helped build mutual understanding.

Big (and small) realizations and what helped (or would have helped)

- We all speak different “languages”, and that's okay.
→ The musician-led exercise helped participants rethink how we “hear” climate change, creating unexpected metaphors.
- Institutions are listening but need better tools.
→ Having city officials and policymakers in the room showed that there's openness, but also a need for fresh formats like this one.

“As a scientist, I believe outreach and engagement should be valued in our careers. While initiatives like the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) are helping change how we evaluate researchers, more institutional change is still needed.”

— Vanessa Sarah Salvo

Smart tags

- Method & Format: Sound-based workshops, Creative storytelling
- Who Was Involved: Musicians, Students, Communicators
- Thematic Focus: Climate awareness, Marine pollution
- Process Style: Youth-oriented, Metaphor-based
- Participation: Active and passive

4. What we learned

4.1. Turning challenges into solutions

Through interviews with artists, scientists, curators, and facilitators working on co-creation projects, we identified recurring challenges and strategies to address them. The insights below offer a reality check and a toolkit for those navigating art-science-community collaboration. At the same time, several of these challenges and solutions also appeared in the Mission Ocean projects referred to in [section 3.1](#). For specific methods or activities see Annex 1: Examples of methods across the co-creation Journey.

"You can't talk about co-creation and then keep decision-making in one room." — Practitioner interviewed

Working across art, science, and communities sounds inspiring, and it is, but it also brings tension. Practitioners consistently pointed to the behind-the-scenes friction that shapes every stage of a participatory process. Here are the most common challenges that emerged from the interview and the ways people worked through them:

Challenge: Scientists disengaging too early

"They show up at the beginning, drop a lecture, and vanish." — Practitioner interviewed

Several projects struggled with scientists stepping out after delivering initial input. This left artists feeling abandoned or unsure how to stay true to science. In one project, the early artworks didn't align well with the science, leading to frustration on both sides.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Setting expectations clearly at the beginning about ongoing participation.
- Introducing mid-process feedback loops.
- Pairing scientists with artists more intentionally.
- Having a scientist-mediator who stayed involved throughout.

In PREP4BLUE, scientists participated in co-design labs where they were not only experts, but co-learners and creative partners. This helped them feel more involved and allowed them to shape the participatory process alongside citizens.

Try these tools:

- “Silent Conversation” ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Create asynchronous shared reflection spaces where scientists and artists can respond to each other’s thinking over time
- Timeline of Transformation ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): At the start of the collaboration use collaboratively mapping key process moments, past, present, and planned, this helps visualize where scientists (and others) are needed and when.

Challenge: Role confusion

"We thought we were here to co-create. They thought we were here to communicate their message." — Practitioner interviewed

Artists in several projects felt pressure to “represent” science while scientists were often unclear whether they were expected to mentor, collaborate, or step back.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Co-defining roles and intentions at the start.
- Revisiting responsibilities as the project evolved.
- Using role-mapping exercises to let people name their own contributions.

In PREP4BLUE⁶, citizen assemblies and co-design labs began with role-mapping sessions, helping participants understand what they were being invited into and how their voice mattered.

Try these tools:

- Role Mapping & Invitation Cards ([SHIFT Toolkit](#)): Lets people define their contribution and reframe roles more as energies than titles.
- Stakeholder Characterisation ([D4C Toolkit](#)): Stakeholder-power-emotion mapping across science-art-citizen roles.
- Prototyping on a Map ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Helps participants visualize where and how each actor is involved spatially and contextually.
- AROSA: Argumentative Role Play ([SHIFT Toolkit](#)): A performative simulation where participants assume fictional stakeholder roles to collaboratively explore tensions, practice negotiation, and reflect on group dynamics.

⁶ PREP4BLUE — Preparing the research and innovation core for Mission Ocean. Co-creation Toolbox and citizen assembly methods. Project resources available at: <https://prep4blue.eu/resources/>

Challenge: Too fast, too tight, too much

"Ten days is enough to start something. But not to go deep."

— Practitioner interviewed

One of the most commonly cited challenges across the interviews was the pressure of time. Short timelines resulted in rushing the relationship-building phase, leading to superficial engagement with local communities. One interviewee spoke of the emotional labour involved when it comes to holding space for reflection, care, and administrative tasks, all while meeting deadlines. Another interviewee described the pressure to run workshops and events while also managing multiple roles as coordinator, communicator, and facilitator.

"Everyone talks about care. But who's taking care of the people holding the care?" — Practitioner interviewed

What helped (or would have helped):

- Even a few informal days of presence can help to build trust and context before the “official” work begins.
- Art residencies should not be treated as isolated events where artists simply create something and leave. Instead, they should be seen as starting points, as the beginning of longer, deeper relationships between artists, communities, scientists, and the local ecosystem.
- Care work and facilitation must be resourced if we want co-creation to be real, not left invisible or unpaid.
- Give creative outcomes the space to grow, instead of forcing them into tight timelines.

Both FLOW and BlueMissionMed prioritized deeper engagement in fewer places over wide reach. They accepted slower rhythms and embraced long-term anchoring in each context.

Try these tools:

- Circle of Objects ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): A quick way to open projects with emotional depth and create early connection between participants
- Foot(notes): A Walking Diary ([SHIFT Toolkit](#), [PREP4BLUE Toolkit](#)): An informal walking practice to gently build trust, observe the environment, and connect emotionally before rushing into activities.
- Reconnection Rituals Canvas ([D4C Toolkit](#)): A set of simple group rituals to make care visible, support emotional well-being, and slow down the pace during intense periods.

Challenge: Participation gaps

Some communities didn't join because of language barriers, bad timing, or formats that felt distant. Events during working hours, missing translators, or complicated invitations made people feel excluded or unsure if the project was really for them. As a result, participation wasn't always as open or diverse as it could have been.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Clear, friendly language and invitations that sounded welcoming, not like official, complicated forms, would help people feel it was for them.
- At the start of an art residency or project, it's important to clearly explain the objectives and methods to the community. This helps build trust, ensures the project is meaningful to them, and allows space for adjusting the approach based on their interests and needs.
- Early engagement with local leaders, neighbourhood or shops associations, schools, or youth organisations among others.
- Having interpreters or at least translated materials in the key languages of the community.
- Meeting people where they already gather (cafés, community events, local markets).
- Scheduling events to match community rhythms (e.g. evenings, weekends).

In the FLOW⁷ project (Mission Ocean), co-creation activities were held inside schools using storytelling and game formats co-designed with teachers. This made participation feel familiar and playful, especially for young people.

Try these tools:

- Stakeholder Characterisation ([D4C Toolkit](#)): Helps identify different community groups and their needs early to plan inclusive engagement.
- Getting to Know Each Other and [HSR](#) Activities ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): Early informal activities to build trust and explain project goals in an accessible way.
- Stories as Insight ([D4C Toolkit](#)): A storytelling method to invite community members to share their own experiences and create a dialogue that feels meaningful to them.

⁷ FLOW — Fostering Local Waterways: Co-creation project for youth and communities. Mission Ocean and Waters EU project. Available at: <https://www.flowhorizon.eu/re-surface-reimagine/>

Challenge: Artistic vs. scientific tension

Some artists struggled to interpret raw scientific data while some scientists were surprised or even confused by the artistic results.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Offering visuals and metaphors instead of raw data.
- Giving artists space to “get it wrong” and iterate.
- Offering creative freedom with lightly structured checkpoints.
- Building trust through informal moments, like shared meals.
- Setting the stage early by defining everyone’s needs, expectations, and creative boundaries.

In Ocean Citizen and BlueMissionMed, artists and scientists collaborated during fieldwork and rituals, rather than separately. This supported more fluid exchange and helped avoid rigid expectations.

Try these tools:

- Golden Circle Exercise ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): A simple tool to align everyone's “why, how, and what” from the start, helping define needs and expectations openly.
- More-Than-Human Intervision ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): A creative, reflective session where participants can explore different perspectives and metaphors rather than only facts.
- Building Visions with Materials ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): A hands-on method that allows artists and scientists to collaborate using objects and visual metaphors instead of only words or data.

Challenge: Evaluation and legacy

"We need creative evaluation methods, not forms that kill the process." — Practitioner interviewed

Projects often lacked structured ways to reflect on what happened, or plan for what came next. Participants were not answering the feedback forms, and, in some projects, the impact was measured through likes or media mentions.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Using creative documentation: reflection circles, message-in-a-bottle exercises.
- Conducting interviews post-project to capture real impact.
- Capturing personal stories, small shifts, and emotional reactions.
- Letting participants co-design the evaluation process so it feels meaningful, not like homework.
- Setting reuse agreements for artworks or outputs ahead of time.

In BlueMission AA⁸, scenario workshops invited communities to explore what long-term transformation could look like and what roles they might keep playing in it.

Try these tools:

- Learning & Commitment ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Ends a process with group reflection on what was learned and what will be carried forward.
- Timeline of Transformation ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Let participants track emotional and process shifts over time, not just outcomes.
- Reflection Circles, Sea Forum Guiding Questions ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): A simple, inclusive way to hold open conversations and gather meaningful feedback without formal surveys.

⁸ BlueMission AA — Atlantic and Arctic basin implementation project under Mission Ocean. Uses scenario workshops and long-term participatory planning. Overview available at: <https://bluemissionaa.eu/>

Challenge: Navigating institutional power

"Policymakers didn't show up, not because they didn't care, but because they didn't feel safe." — Practitioner interviewed

Working with institutions (governments, funders, schools, cultural bodies) often means going through bureaucracy, and status hierarchies. Several practitioners described difficulty getting policymakers to attend debates, hesitance from schools to engage youth on “sensitive” issues, or the pressure to produce impact that fits funder language. Institutions were often supportive in theory, but distant in practice.

Despite the tension, practitioners developed strategies to lean into complexity instead of erasing it: Marta's role in Thalastasi was to gently hold space between artists and scientists, translating needs and softening friction. Transparent roles and expectations helped reduce misunderstandings. Nora and Nicole both emphasized clear agreements and human-centered onboarding. The need to be upfront about what's possible, what's flexible, and who gets to decide what. Isidora began her projects with “nothing”: no agenda, no schedule. Just a shared space.

What helped (or would have helped):

- Creating safe, solutions-oriented spaces for dialogue, rather than confrontational ones.
- Speaking their language when needed, framing the project in terms of the institution's priorities without losing the soul of the work.
- Using informal settings (like festivals, or youth-led formats) to lower barriers.
- Setting honest expectations early about what participation would (and wouldn't) look like.
- Involving institutions as co-authors, not only validators or funders.

In Ocean Citizen⁹, institutional actors joined early sessions in the role of listeners, not leaders. Meetings were held in community settings, allowing non-experts to express themselves more freely. In BlueMissionMed¹⁰, participatory events were designed with local partners in villages and small coastal communities. Institutions were invited into those spaces rather than expecting participants to come to them.

⁹ Ocean Citizen. An underwater forestation project combining restoration science with public engagement. Horizon Europe project. Available at: <https://www.oceancitizen.eu>

¹⁰ BlueMissionMed — Mediterranean basin-focused Mission Ocean implementation project. Includes citizen engagement, foresight, and co-creation at local scale. Available at: <https://bluemissionmed.eu/>

Try these tools:

- The Beehive: Exploring Alternative Futures ([SHIFT Toolkit](#)): A participatory method that frames dialogue around collective imagination and solutions
- Silent Conversation ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): A non-verbal method that invites all participants, including policymakers, to express ideas safely without fear of immediate judgment.
- Creative Partnerships for Urban Rivers ([SHIFT Toolkit](#)): A co-creation framework that positions institutions as active collaborators in creative, place-based initiatives

4.2. Lessons from the field

"You can't arrive with an idea and expect people to follow it. You have to let go, be changed by the encounter."
— Practitioner interviewed

Although the initial intention was to find concrete methodologies and how-to guides, these interviews showed us that co-creation is all about sharing moments; moments of clarity, tension and surprise. And these are the lessons that can only be discovered through practice.

Build trust before anything else

"The conditions for trust aren't a 'nice-to-have', they are the project." — Practitioner interviewed

The projects that went furthest took time to build relationships before building content and finally products. Vanessa Salvo (Posidonia Green Festival) collaborated with musicians and schools to co-create playful, metaphor-based workshops about climate change. Her work emphasized emotional safety and creative entry points for youth. Jordi (Co-Vision) involved locals in setting the festival's themes months in advance, so their needs shaped the programming, not the other way around. Aleksandra (OCEAN / UNI. Activation series) prioritized emotional safety in OCEAN / UNI's fellowships, creating rhythms of care alongside research. Overall, strong connections that are built during collaborations often spark friendships, new projects, and years of mutual support.

Flexibility is key

Projects that didn't leave room to adapt often struggled. The ones that embraced change, even mid-process, found themselves with more aligned outcomes.

When a planned artist-scientist pairing wasn't flowing, an interviewee restructured the collaboration:

"We realized it wasn't working, and it was better to shift, even if it meant changing the plan mid-way."

— Practitioner interviewed

In one collaboration, an interviewee stepped into an informal facilitation role, adjusting the process midway to help scientists and artists make sense both on the format and expectations. In Thalastasi, the team continuously adapted scientific content and language to respond to artists' needs and community dynamics by adjusting narratives, formats, and timing based on continuous feedback.

Scientists need reasons to participate too

"The incentive is visibility, finding new ways to tell your story and reaching different publics. But they won't dare do it unless someone helps them. They don't have time, they might not feel confident, and they need a person who can guide them through it." — Practitioner interviewed

Some interviewees noted that the real incentive for scientists is visibility, new ways of explaining their work, reaching new audiences or even discovering something new through the artistic lens. But they also need someone by their side, someone who understands the process, helps shape it, and makes sure it doesn't demand too much time.

Internal motivation matters but may not be enough

"The problem is that there's no education around this. If you don't have a personal reason, no scientist is going to get involved. It's a field that feels so far away. That's why we need internal, institutional work."

— Practitioner interviewed

Many scientists and institutional actors engage in co-creation only when they have a personal connection to art, or a strong individual interest. Relying only on personal curiosity can't sustain collaboration in the long term. What's missing, several interviewees noted, is internal infrastructure, people don't engage with what they don't understand or see valued.

Let the process emerge

"It's not about making science visible. It's about creating space for something new to take shape."

— Practitioner interviewed

The most powerful outcomes didn't come from perfect planning, they came from letting go. Isidora (Forensic river) started with trust: local youth decided the topics, formats, and rhythm of each session. "Our method was listening first" she said. Eduardo (Organismo) described co-creation as "a spiral, not a sequence." Some of the most important work happened between activities, in kitchens, during rituals, or in silence.

We don't all see the same thing

"Everyone saw something different. "Scientists, artists - even I saw beauty where others only saw disaster. That's bias. And that's the starting point for real dialogue.""

— Practitioner interviewed

Personal bias shaped by discipline, emotion, or context influences how participants perceive both process and outcomes. Many interviewees described moments where people interpreted the same artwork, data, or experience in entirely different ways. Recognizing these filters as the first step toward more honest, curious, and collaborative work.

Documentation

"The most important document isn't the one we write—it's what people think is happening." — Practitioner interviewed

Isidora (Forensic river) ended her project with a co-created performance built from participants' own language and then asked them how it felt. For her, the most important document wasn't what was written down, but what people believed was happening. Jordi (Co-Vision) worked with a graphic narrator that visually recorded the day's events and emotions, with audio recordings and sketches. Nora (CircEUlar) helped develop a series of short online videos to share the collaboration between artists and scientists. The team also created a booklet and visual materials like postcards and video artworks, with legal agreements allowing reuse. Thalastasi team archived process discussions and creative exchanges in a shared online space and later recommended to include a visual or ethnographic narrator in the project budget to better capture the flow of collaboration.

5. How to Design Co-Creation (Step by Step)

After listening to artists, scientists, and mediators working in festivals, labs, residencies, and community spaces, shared patterns began to emerge: in what they learned, and in how they worked. This section draws on those lived experiences and combines them with practical tools to offer a step-by-step guide to designing participatory processes. It's a flexible structure that can support artists, scientists, and community facilitators as they shape their own co-creation. This section is organised around three key stages: before, during, and after engagement and uses real-world insights and tested methods to help design processes that are inclusive, intentional, and rooted in care.

"We didn't wait to start until the project was funded. We were already there, listening." — Practitioner interviewed

One of the most consistent lessons from these interviews? Participation is not a step in the process, it is the process. The strongest projects were not the ones of a single workshop or public event, but the ones that were designed as evolving relationships that began early, adapted throughout, and often continued after formal timelines ended.

5.1. Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation

"You don't land with a workshop; you arrive with curiosity."
— Practitioner interviewed.

Across the board, practitioners stressed that the real work starts before any project formally begins. Isidora (Forensic river) described showing up for months without a plan: just listening, asking questions, joining local rhythms, until trust grew naturally. Jordi (Co-Vision) spoke about shifting from "inviting people to participate" to "co-creating what participation even means." This stage isn't about preparing materials; it's about preparing relationships. The projects that got somewhere meaningful started by letting go of control early, staying open to surprise, and treating the community as co-authors from day one.

Practical Steps:

1. Map the territory and the voices.

- Who's here? • Who's missing? • What tensions or hopes exist?
- What are the frustrations and needs?

Identify early who your stakeholders are (scientists, youth groups, artists, local activists, neighbourhood or water related communities), their actual concerns and existing knowledge systems.

2. Invite early and build trust before “the process”:

Isidora walked neighbourhoods for weeks before presenting any framework, learning what people cared about. Macarena Marambio (Art4Sea) discovered local fishing communities weren't always enthusiastic to participate; if they had spent more time in the field before the residencies, she believes relationships might have been better.

3. Slow down and listen:

Before starting formal activities, spend informal time with communities, asking open questions, and understanding daily realities.

4. Be explicit about roles:

Clearly define expectations and roles (artists, scientists, mediators) upfront to reduce confusion or disappointment later.

5. Communicate creatively:

Adapt your language and approach to different groups (e.g., using music and emotional storytelling for young audiences, starting from concepts or ideas that your audience already knows about and is interested in).

Key questions to ask yourself at this stage:

- Who's not at the table and why?
- What do people care about here?
- And how do they talk about it?
- Are we building interest or assuming it?
- Are the project goals and individual roles crystal clear to all involved?
- Is our communication style genuinely accessible and attractive to the audiences we most want to engage?

Try these tools:

- Circle of Objects ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Ask participants to bring an object representing their connection to water.
- Prototyping on a Map ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Map places that matter to them. For example, in a coastal town, marine scientists and young residents worked together to draw places they felt connected to (i.e. fishing spots, polluted rivers, and beaches they loved). This brings up emotional ties to the ocean that later may shape the themes of the artistic residency.
- Reconnection Rituals Canvas ([D4C Toolkit](#)): This activity asks to recall personal experiences with the sea, and their memories will be used to inspire artists.
- Walking interviews ([PREP4BLUE Toolkit](#)): To explore participants' needs, knowledge, and relationships to their environment before starting any workshop or residency.

More methods like these can be found in the Annex 1.

5.2. Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation

"Co-creation doesn't mean sharing the table. It means rebuilding it together." — Practitioner interviewed.

The moment people step into the space, everything changes. Eduardo (Organismo) called it “structured chaos”, a space where real collaboration can only happen when you allow for mess, silence, friction, and joy. Aleksandra (OCEAN / UNI. Activation series) emphasized finding a balance between giving participants space and offering enough support to keep momentum. For another interviewee, sound and metaphor were ways to let students lead the learning, not just receive it. Nicole’s tools (Art for Future Labs) offered structure without rigidity, letting citizens and scientists map the future together through visuals, emotion, and dialogue.

Example:

Isidora Fernandez (Science4Change) — Transforming a Community Lab into a ‘Crime Scene’

- **What happened:** Isidora wanted to spark curiosity about local water pollution in a high-vulnerability neighbourhood. So, she decorated the small community lab like a forensic crime scene: caution tape, evidence boards, lab coats.
- **How it worked:** Instead of simply telling them about microplastics or water toxins, she let people act as forensic investigators. Adults and kids gathered samples, analysed them, and gradually assembled a case. Everyone was a detective.
- **Key insight:** Role-playing made the co-creation playful. Even the local teens, normally unenthusiastic, took the lead, feeling ownership of the “mystery.” Isidora calls it “immersive science” where participants become part of the story.

Practical Steps

- **Blend tools:**
Use both structured methods (e.g. world-building) and open-ended approaches (rituals, walks, improvisation). Employ methods like scenario workshops, empathy mapping, and backcasting (working backwards from a desired future) to create shared visions and actionable plans (Nicole Loeser, Sustainable Coastal Futures)
- **Support translation:**
Consider a mediator or facilitator who helps artists, scientists, and citizens understand each other.
- **Choose inclusive venues:**
Host sessions in accessible spaces (festivals, public squares, local associations) rather than formal institutions, reducing barriers to entry.

Key questions to ask yourself at this stage:

- What methods let different types of knowledge (scientific, emotional, cultural) meet and reshape each other?
- Do our activities truly allow participants to shape the outcomes, or are we steering too strongly?
- Have we used creative, accessible formats that allow everyone, not just the confident speakers, to contribute?
- What needs to be loosened for something unexpected to emerge?

Try these tools:

- Silent Conversation ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): People write their thoughts silently on a big piece of paper. The question is something like “What would the ocean say today?” or “What kind of future do you want for the sea?” Everyone answers in writing, no talking. Later, these messages turn into a short performance or a shared story.
- Inviting Non-Human Stakeholders ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): Participants adopt the perspective of sea creatures to co-write a shared vision for local waters.
- Forensic Lab Setup (Isidora, Forensic River) — Use a playfully serious role-play (crime scene for water pollution) to explore data hands-on.

Full list of co-creation methods, including sensory and sound-based ones, can be found in the Annex 1.

5.3. Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy

"What stays with people isn't what they did, it's how it made them feel." — Practitioner interviewed.

Reflection, in these projects, wasn't about measuring success. It was about creating space for participants to metabolize what happened together. Isidora Fernandez (Forensic river) asked young people how the performance made them feel. Nora Mayr (CircEUlar) made sure documentation wasn't just archived, but shared in ways people could revisit. Nicole Loeser (Sustainable Coastal Futures) reminded us that long-term impact often comes from the relationships and networks that outlast the project itself. What matters isn't just what was delivered, but what continues to resonate, connect, or grow afterward.

Practical Steps:

- Document creatively and continuously:

Capture the co-creation process with visual notes, short videos, graphic facilitation, or audio recordings. In each session, invite two different participants to document what happens, whether through writing, drawing, or other creative means, and collect these contributions in a shared "living" notebook. In this way, we could help build a collective memory of the process from multiple viewpoints.

- Value emotional reflection:

After events, ask participants about feelings and perceptions ([Profile of Mood States \(POMS\)](#)). Don't just ask what people learned, ask how it landed.

- Keep engagement alive:

Use small rewards or virtual prizes to keep participants motivated, and offer simple follow-up tools like booklets, videos, or online spaces to help communities stay connected and continue the work beyond the residency.

- Design outputs for reuse:

Design the outputs of the residency/project (artworks, tools, or materials) so that they can be reused, adapted, or built upon by the community, making sure the impact lasts beyond the initial project.

Key questions to ask yourself at this stage:

- What do people need to feel after/during the closure?
- Have we captured the participant experiences, beyond just reporting outcomes?
- What strategies are in place to keep participants engaged after the official end date?
- What are we leaving behind, and what are we taking with us?

Try these tools:

- Timeline of Transformation ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)) — Co-create a visual timeline showing what shifted for participants over time.
- Photography with Intervention ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Participants take photos of their daily life near the sea. Later, they add drawings, words, or symbols on top. These photos become part of an exhibition. This helps them tell their personal story and share it with others in a creative way.
- Reflection Circle ([BoSS Toolkit](#)): Participants express what they've learned and felt during the project to strengthen collective insight and memory.
- Theory of Change ([Reimaginary Toolkit](#)): Participants define and track the intended impacts of co-creation activities using shared goals and simple [indicators](#).
- Message in a Bottle ([FLOW Project](#)) — Ask participants to write a letter to the future, or to the sea itself, as a closing act.
- Certificates of Participation (2033 Rights Declaration) ([FLOW Project](#)). As part of the ecosystem rights game, participants receive a personalized certificate from a fictional “International Council for Nature Rights,” to reinforce emotional commitment to the discussed futures

You can find more reflection and legacy tools in the Annex 1.

Conclusion: Understanding the Stakeholders and their Perspectives

This conclusion draws from the full journey of the guide, from Mission Ocean & Waters projects and practitioner stories to tools, patterns, and practical steps. What follows brings those threads together, not as a summary, but as an invitation.

After listening to these eleven practitioners, across islands, festivals, schools, labs, and artistic residencies, one thing is clear: there is no single way to build a co-creation process. But there are patterns and principles that keep showing up. Artists shared that they are eager to collaborate, but they need more than just a seat at the table, they want to shape the table. They ask for trust, time, and freedom to create without being boxed into outreach roles. They thrive when the creative process is allowed to stay messy, emotional, and full of surprises. Scientists want collaboration that respects both rigor and emotion, finding new ways to tell their stories without losing scientific depth. Citizens made it clear: participation isn't about being asked for opinions once but about real involvement. They want to co-create from the start, to see their knowledge and experiences woven into the work, not added on at the end. When citizens feel seen, they bring local textures, emotional truths, and bold imagination into the mix.

Across all these voices, we hear a call for processes built on care, reciprocity, and genuine shared authorship.

- Start with presence, not a plan.
- Design with people, not for them.
- Let the process change you, not just the participants.
- Trust takes time. So does real collaboration.
- Make room for discomfort, it's part of the work.

While these conversations shaped the heart of the guide, they sit alongside the larger efforts already underway in Mission Ocean & Waters projects (for example, PREP4BLUE, FLOW, BlueMissionMed, BlueMissionAA, BlueMission BANOS and Ocean Citizen). These projects have tested co-creation in alignment with the Mission through citizen assemblies, youth storytelling, local mapping, or future visioning. They remind us that structured frameworks and community experimentation can meet, inform and strengthen each other. Together, they help us imagine a culture of participation that's both ambitious and rooted in real places and relationships.

The co-creation approaches outlined in this guide directly support the citizen engagement, social inclusion, and stewardship objectives set out in Mission Ocean & Waters. The methods encourage active public involvement, empower diverse groups to take ownership of local water challenges, and strengthen connections between cultural creativity and environmental action, by fostering deep collaboration between artists, scientists, and communities. Through this, they help build resilient Lighthouse communities committed to ocean and water restoration.

The annexes that follow offer additional methods, tools, and guidance to support the practical application of the ideas explored in this guide.

Resources and Further Reading

A selection of toolkits, platforms, and reading materials for those who want to go deeper, get inspired, or try things out in their own contexts.

- Bauhaus of the Seas Sails: Co-design
[Resources and Further Reading](#)
- D4C Toolkit: Design for Conservation
<https://www.design4conservation.com/d4c-toolkit>
- Reimaginary Toolkit: Arts-Based Methods for Transformative Engagement
<https://www.reimaginary.com/search-methods-resources7>
- SHIFT Toolkit: Creative and arts-based methods for regeneration and transformation that can be used in various educational settings
https://shift-cost.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Final-Toolkit_compressed.pdf
- The Collective Body: Collective Imagination and Social Imagination - Somatics, Relationships and Entanglements
<https://www.collectiveimagination.tools/toolkit-index#collective-body>
- PREP4BLUE Toolkit: Toolbox for Citizen Engagement
<https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>
- YouCount: Handbook and Toolkit for Youth Citizen Social Science
<https://www.youcountproject.eu/resources/project-reports>
- A collection of ongoing citizen science projects across disciplines and countries.
<https://eu-citizen.science/projects>
- Toolkits, guidelines, and case studies for designing and evaluating citizen science initiatives
<https://eu-citizen.science/resources>

Annex 1

Examples of methods across the co-creation journey

This annex gathers examples of co-creation methods that can be used during different stages of a co-creation process: before engagement begins, during participatory activities, and after, during reflection and legacy building. Each method includes suggestions for when to use it, who it can involve (see Annex 2 for an overview of the audiences these methods aim to engage), and where to find more information. The table is followed by a conceptual map that includes the same concepts as the table.

The examples are intended to inspire flexible, creative, and inclusive approaches that artists, scientists, and communities can adapt to their local contexts and needs.

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Prototyping on a Map	Before residencies & Lighthouse calls	Marine advocates, scientists, artists, digitally & non-digitally literate individuals, underrepresented communities	link	p. 49
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Collaborative Maps of Curiosity	Before residencies & Lighthouse calls	Marine advocates, scientists, artists, underrepresented communities, educators, policymakers	link	p. 21
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Stakeholder Characterisation	Before residencies & Lighthouse calls	All target audiences	link	
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Scale Shift & Mapping Drift	Pre-engagement & site visits	Scientists, educators, policymakers, underrepresented groups	link	p. 37

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Future and Nature Stakeholder Integration	Pre-engagement & site visits	Policymakers, educators, community leaders, marine advocates	link	p. 25
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Foot(notes): A Walking Diary	Pre-engagement & site visits	Artists, students, community members	link	p. 49
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Conservation Challenge Canvas	Pre-engagement & site visits	All target audiences	link	
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Reconnection Rituals Canvas	Pre-engagement & site visits	Underrepresented/ minority communities, Non-English speaking/ older people	link	
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Golden Circle Exercise	Pre-engagement & site visits	All target audiences	link	p. 23
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Getting to Know Each Other and HSR activities	Pre-engagement & site visits	All target audiences	link	p. 26

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Walking interviews	Pre-engagement & site visits	All target audiences	link	
Stage 1: Pre-Engagement & Preparation	Stories as Insight	First day of residencies/ workshops	All target audiences	link	
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Identifying "Speakers for the Living" and Non-Human Stakeholders	Pre-engagement & site visits	All target audiences	link	p. 22
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Embodied Transformation Theatre	First day of residencies/ workshops	Artists, educators, students, policymakers	link	p. 53
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Building Visions with Materials	During co-creation labs, residencies, or interactive workshops	All target audiences	link	p.18, p.27
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Inviting Non-Human Stakeholders	During residencies & field-based labs	Marine advocates, scientists, artists, digitally & non-digitally literate individuals	link	p. 38

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Storytelling	Throughout residencies & public engagement	Artists, students, non-digitally literate individuals, underrepresented communities	link	p. 31
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Prototyping on a Map	During residencies & participatory planning sessions	Artists, scientists, urban planners, local policymakers, community members	link	p. 49
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Evoking the Senses	During co-creation labs, residencies, or interactive workshops	Artists, creatives, marine educators, non-digitally literate individuals, underrepresented communities	link	p. 28
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Collaborative Soundscapes	Throughout residencies, interactive performances, or public engagement events	Musicians, artists, scientists, local communities, youth groups, underrepresented communities	link	p. 18
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Embodied Knowledge Practices	During residencies, movement-based workshops, and interactive labs	Artists, scientists, local communities, marine advocates	link	p. 42
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Circle of objects	During co-creation events, community gatherings, or participatory festivals	Cultural practitioners, artists, local community members, non-digitally literate individuals	link	p. 34

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Silent Conversation	Throughout residencies and workshops focused on imagining future ocean-human relations	Artists, scientists, policymakers, youth groups, educators, underrepresented communities	link	p. 50
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Creative Partnerships for Urban Rivers	During residencies & field-based labs	Artists, scientists, community members, students	link	p. 45
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Ecotheatre as a Tool of Environmental Imaginary	Throughout residencies & public engagement	Theatre practitioners, marine advocates, students	link	p. 71
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Immersive Field Trip	During residencies & field-based labs	Artists/Creatives, Marine & freshwater scientists, Citizens	link	
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Agile Interviews	During co-creation events, community gatherings, or participatory festivals	Citizens, Community leaders	link	
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Inspired Ideation Lotus	Throughout residencies & public engagement	Artists/Creatives, Marine & freshwater scientists	link	

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Botanical Empathy	During residencies, movement-based workshops, and interactive labs	Artists/Creatives, Citizens	link	
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	More-Than-Human Intervention	Midpoint evaluations	Scientists, artists, citizens, decision-makers, underrepresented communities	link	p. 45
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	The Living Canvas: Community Mural Creation	Midpoint evaluations	Community members, underrepresented groups	link	p. 87
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Photography with Intervention	End of residencies & participatory projects	Artists, photographers, community members	link	p. 83
Stage 2: Co-Creation & Participation	Regenerative Futures with Children: The Radio Approach	Final sessions, follow-up engagement	Youth, educators, underrepresented groups	link	p. 109
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Feedback and Iteration Tool	Throughout residencies and workshops focused on imagining future ocean-human relations	All participants	link	

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Imagination Activation Exercise: What If	Throughout residencies and workshops focused on imagining future ocean-human relations	Creative thinkers, educators, activists	link	p. 129
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Narrating New Future Visions	Throughout residencies, interactive performances, or public engagement events	Activists, educators, non-English speakers	link	p. 105
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Stakeholder Motivation Matrix	During residencies & participatory planning sessions	Participants, Community organizations	link	
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Tales of Transformation: Climate Justice Narratives	During residencies & participatory planning sessions	Artists, activists, educators, underrepresented groups	link	p. 121
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	The Beehive — Exploring Alternative Futures	During co-creation labs, residencies, or interactive workshops	Policymakers, community leaders, artists	link	p. 117
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Future Visioning as a Tool for Imagining Regenerative and Sustainable Futures	During residencies, movement-based workshops, and interactive labs	Students, educators, policymakers	link	p. 137

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Participatory Evaluation (Theory of Change)	Midpoint evaluations	Citizens, Community leaders	link	p.30-31
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Impact Planning Tool	Midpoint evaluations, End of residencies & participatory projects	Community members, Project stakeholders	link	
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Reflection Circles (Sea forum guiding questions)	End of residencies & participatory projects	All target audiences	link	p.30-31
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Creative Harvest	End of residencies & participatory projects	Artists, workshop participants, policymakers, museum curators, underrepresented communities	link	p. 56
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Semi-structured interviews	End of residencies & participatory projects	Artists/Creatives, Citizens, Scientists	link	
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Sustainable Growth Plan	Final sessions, follow-up engagement	Participants, Wider community	link	

Stages of co-creation	Method	When do we do this?	Audience	Source	Toolkit Page Reference
Stage 3: Reflection, Documentation & Legacy	Learning & Commitment	Final sessions, follow-up engagement	Community members, artists, youth groups, environmental NGOs, underrepresented communities	link	p. 59

See conceptual mapping version of this table [here](#) or below.

Methodology links

https://shift-cost.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Final-Toolkit_compressed.pdf

<https://www.design4conservation.com/conservation-challenge>

https://bauhaus-seas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Bauhaus_of_the_Seas_Sails_co-designtemplate_2023.pdf

<https://prep4blue.eu/portfolio/toolbox-for-citizen-engagement/>

<https://www.reimaginary.com/search-methods-resources>

Annex 2

Audience analysis

One of the central challenges identified early in Mission Ocean & Waters was the emotional distance many people feel from marine issues. As Pascal Lamy put it, there is “a gap between the importance of oceans and waters on one side, and the very little knowledge and emotional connection that many people have with this, on the other.” TIDAL ArtS responds to this gap by working with two broad types of audiences: those who already feel a connection to the ocean, and those who don’t - yet. Each group requires different approaches. Those already engaged may be inspired to act more deeply or connect with the Mission’s goals . For others, the priority is to build emotional connection and awareness first. This section introduces these two target groups and the specific communities we aim to reach through arts-science engagement.

Target Audience 1: People with an emotional connection to ocean & waters	
Aim:	Increase “Mission Literacy”; inspire action.
Target sub-groups:	Marine advocates, Marine & freshwater scientists, Artists/Creatives, Digitally literate, Non-digitally literate/interested, English speaking students, Underrepresented/minority communities, Non-English speaking/older people.
Target Audience 2: People without an emotional connection to ocean & waters	
Aim:	Increase ocean literacy; establish emotional connection.
Target sub-groups:	Digitally Literate, Artists/Creatives, Non-digitally literate/interested, English speaking students, Underrepresented/minority communities, Non-English speaking/older people.

Target sub-group	Description
Marine advocates:	People who are already engaged in marine topics, projects, or activities, either professionally or voluntarily. They could come from a wide age range and cultural backgrounds. They might be motivated by activities that align with or amplify their chosen cause, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.
Marine & freshwater scientists	People who are trained in marine and freshwater science or social science. They might work as part of Mission Ocean & Waters-funded project teams or other related research and innovation initiatives. They might be motivated activities that align with their area of expertise, amplify their chosen cause or community of interest, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.
Artists/Creatives:	People working formally or informally in the arts and culture sector. Alternatively, people with an interest and talent in arts and creative practice but for who this is not a job. These people might be motivated to engage with TIDAL ArtS for networking opportunities, to amplify their chosen cause or community of interest, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.
Digitally literate:	Those who are likely to engage or want to engage with ocean science-arts initiatives through digital means. They might be motivated by participation opportunities in digital citizen science initiatives, digital art-science activities, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.
Non-digitally literate/interested:	Those for whom the digital represents a barrier in terms of accessibility. Either they do not have the means nor the skills needed to engage with digital methods. They may also simply be uninterested in digital forms of engagement. They might be motivated by activities that align with or amplify their chosen cause, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.
English speaking students:	English is often used as the principal language of multi-partner, multi-state projects. University students who can engage in English is one target group for TIDAL ArtS. This group might also be interested in the academic aspects of engagement and motivated by the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.

Target sub-group	Description
<p>Underrepresented/ minority communities:</p>	<p>These are groups that are not usually included or otherwise find themselves sidelined from participation in art-science initiatives.</p> <p>These will vary depending on the region and usually require higher levels of outreach and perhaps separate or extra engagements to reach successfully.</p> <p>They might be motivated by a sense of being included, learning about their new community's marine heritage and resources, the offer of academic credentials, co-authorship on papers, monetary and other forms of compensation.</p>
<p>Non-English speaking/ older people:</p>	<p>People who will not participate or find it difficult to participate in English speaking activities. These groups need to be engaged using an intermediary, by hiring bilingual facilitators, or running bilingual events. Depending on their other attributes, they might be motivated by any of the options listed above.</p> <p>If social isolation is an issue, older people might also be motivated by the opportunity to engage with their wider community as part of initiatives.</p>

Annex 3

Quick Guide for Artists or Creatives

"You don't land with a workshop. You arrive with curiosity."
— Practitioner interviewed.

Before You Start

- Know the local context:
 - Who lives here? What are the local water-related challenges? What emotions connect people to the sea, river, or place?
- Ask simple but deep questions to scientists:
 - What problem are you trying to solve? What story does this research tell?
 - Choose scientists who are accessible, and select topics that are easy to understand while sparking emotion and interest.
 - Involve people from the beginning
 - Try to meet or speak with participants before the first activity.
- Include diverse voices:
 - Consider language, age, gender, education (etc.) and create invitations that feel welcoming and easy to understand.
- Give clear messages and instructions from the start, including the objectives, discuss the timelines, the roles of different collaborators.
- Create ground rules that prevent harsh criticism
- Be ready to adapt: Your first idea will probably change, and that's part of the magic.

During the Process

- Make space for every voice:
 - People bring different types of knowledge. Use multiple ways for people to express themselves: drawing, movement, music, speaking, silent writing.
- Your creativity is central, and it's more powerful when it reflects Mission Ocean's objectives.
- Be ready to adapt: Plans will change. Weather will change. Emotions will change. Stay flexible and curious.
- Build on different points of view, don't let the discussions get stuck in a conflict.
- Try to use relators and mediators
- Share drafts early
 - Show unfinished work to participants, not to get judgment, but to grow the idea together.

After the Activity

- Reflect together: Ask “How did this feel?” and “What should we do next?”
- Share outcomes clearly: Even if the project is small, make sure people know what came out of it
- Think about legacy: Can the work live on? In schools? In local organisations? In memories?
- Think how could participants be spokespersons for the project? By giving them simple tools and encouraging them to share their experiences through events, social media, or community spaces.

Key Tips

- Use visuals and materials that are easy to understand, without oversimplifying the concepts.
- Partner with trusted local organisations to open doors and hearts.
- Don't rush the process, even short projects need time for connection.
- Respect different rhythms: science, art, and communities all move differently. Let them.
- Create informal spaces and moments for spontaneous exchange, choose locations that inspire, welcome everyone, and connect directly to the project's themes.
- Use the local language during participatory activities to ensure full inclusion, better understanding, and emotional connection.

Annex 4

Our decalogue for art - science - community co-creation

1. Clarify the "why" of the collaboration:

Be explicit about whether the goal is co-creation, inspiration, education, or outreach. Set expectations early, including roles, timelines, and levels of artistic and scientific freedom.

2. Always include a mediator

A dedicated person (scientific, artistic, or hybrid) should bridge disciplines, help translate language, and guide mutual understanding. Without this, dialogue might become parallel monologues.

3. Start with trust, not tasks

Don't jump straight into content. Invest in relationship-building through informal meetings, shared meals, or site visits. Trust is the foundation of true collaboration. Build trust by acknowledging the vulnerability of sharing personal work.

4. Design for participation, not presentation

Don't just extract opinions or expect attendance, co-create from the start. Invite diverse voices to shape the process, not just react to it.

5. Use inclusive and flexible methods

Adapt methods to the context. What works in Italy may not work in Finland; allow each group to shape their approach.

6. Make the invisible visible

Highlight not just the artwork or research, but the process, negotiations, tensions, and breakthroughs. Share the behind-the-scenes as part of the story.

7. Enable mutual literacy

Artists don't need to become scientists, but should understand the research. Scientists don't need to become artists, but should engage with the creative process. Design time and tools for both sides to learn from each other.

8. Allow for imperfection and surprise

Don't force a pretty output. Some of the most powerful results are "beautiful failures" that open new questions or challenge assumptions.

9. Plan for continuity

If possible, embed long-term relationships and pathways. What happens after the exhibition or art residency? Think about legacy from the start.

10. Measure what matters

Capture shifts in mindset, new relationships, and unexpected outcomes, beyond media visibility or participant numbers. Evaluation should reflect the richness of the process.

TIDAL Arts

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
Art and Sciences

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